

Európai Unió
Európai Regionális
Fejlesztési Alap

BEFEKTETÉS A JÖVŐBE

Hercules Routes

*Presentation of business requirements,
business processes and statistics*

GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364

Arnold Horváth

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1. Abstract

The purpose of this document is to describe the business requirements identified during the development of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules routes" identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364 and to describe the business processes and statistics of the system resulting from the implementation.

The final result of the development of the Hercules Routes framework is a specific artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for companies transporting their employees and for companies contracted to transport their employees. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (passenger vehicles) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

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2. Introduction

Since the emergence of industrial parks in our country, intensive long-distance transport has been developed around industrial parks to cover the needs of commuting to and from work. These long-distance services are, with some exceptions, typically by bus and can cover an area of up to 50-60 km around the industrial estate. Unfortunately, the transport service providers contracting with the factories have no interest in optimising these routes, as they typically contract for fixed-route services, including the distance travelled. Such fixed-route services result in underutilised travel capacity and often half-empty services, imposing unjustified costs on the contracting factories and causing unjustified pollution and noise in the surrounding villages. To make matters worse, the factories located in industrial parks do not group their transport needs together but order them separately from the transport service providers, thus increasing travel costs and burdening the environment.

Focusing on this problem, we aim to implement a service package that optimises long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. Although ready-made software systems for road freight transport have been available for a long time, at the beginning of our work in 2016 there was no solution available on the market for passenger transport, so we decided to develop an R&D-based system of our own design.

From a scientific point of view, the problem is an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem, a special kind of the famous vehicle routing problem (VRP). Due to the well-known difficulty of the problem, the running time of exact algorithms that give perfect results can take several days or even weeks, and therefore these solutions can only be run on small-scale theoretical problems. In practice, a wide range of approximate algorithms are used instead, such as evolutionary algorithm, particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony optimization (ACO), artificial bee colony optimization (ABC), simulated annealing, tabusearch algorithm (TS). Although the runtime of these solutions can be measured in minutes, their major drawback is that the quality of the resulting solution cannot be guaranteed, is not known, and on average they only reach the 95% level (gap = 5%).

The framework we developed is based on artificial intelligence adapted to changing weather and traffic conditions, which is able to predict the average speed of the road sections at any given time, and thus the expected arrival times, from continuously logged GPS data. We formulated the vehicle routing problem as a mixed integer linear programming model to achieve guaranteed quality results. The expected high computational performance was ensured by implementing our own R&D-based heuristics.

Our key requirements for the system were:

- Computational requirements:
 - Complexity: handling up to 500 bus stops and 50 vehicles per industrial park
 - Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
 - High performance calculation, i.e. short calculation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Infrastructure requirements:
 - AI-based self-learning framework
 - Flexible and scalable framework
 - Immediate and complete data delivery
- Expectations:
 - Expected 20% cost reduction through optimisation
 - Reduction of pollution and noise
 - Punctuality, elimination of connecting flights
 - Reduction in administrative time

The development of the "Hercules Routes" framework has resulted in a specialised artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for

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companies that transport their employees and for companies contracted to transport their drivers. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (buses) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

The purpose of this document is to describe the business requirements identified during the development of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364, and to describe the business processes and statistics of the system resulting from its implementation.

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3. Business requirements

3.1. IT environment

3-1. figure: IT environment

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3.2. Roles

Users can be assigned to authorization roles, and a user can be assigned to more than one role at a time. Privileges are assigned to roles and each privilege represents the access to a function. The roles defined by default in the system are described below.

3-2. figure: Roles

3.3. Infrastructure requirements

Infrastructure requirements of the system:

- AI-based self-learning framework:
 - Automated route network construction
 - Automated vehicle prioritization
 - Vehicle placement learning support
 - Management of custom shift definitions
 - Automated HR demand generation
 - Weather and traffic conditions learning
 - R&D based algorithms during calculation
 - R&D based computational heuristics
 - Possibility of using different evaluators
 - Cache based route network pattern recognition
 - Combined optimisation of travel to work and home
- System flexibility and scalability:
 - Any number of factories
 - Any number of passenger transport companies
 - Adaptive adjustment to changing circumstances
 - Self- learning of territorial specificities
- Immediate and complete data delivery:
 - Integrated information service platforms:

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- GPS device and app on buses
- TV display in factories
- Mobile apps
- Mobile website
- Pdf bus-schedule
- Real-time vehicle tracking and information
- Dynamic bus-schedule update and delay notification
- Aggregated and detailed reports
- Detailed route plan

3.4. Passenger transport expectations

Passenger transport expectations of the system:

- Demand management
 - Demands can come from several factories at the same time.
 - There are different ways to collect demand data, some options are non-exhaustive:
 - For demands depending on shift schedules by generating from shift schedules,
 - Based on manually recorded needs.
 - Addressing the problem of transport to work and transport home together is more economical than optimising them separately.
 - The combination of needs by vehicle and by station may be limited in the collection of needs, which should be taken into account in the optimisation.
- Fleet management
 - The vehicles in the insured fleet may come from several owners at the same time.
 - Each type of vehicle may differ, affecting the optimisation according to the following criteria:
 - Vehicle capacity,
 - Vehicle site,
 - Vehicle runtime limit - the time frame available to complete the optimisation task,
 - Vehicle weather factor - weather-dependent speed limit,
 - Vehicle prioritisation options,
 - Variable costs (fuel costs).
 - Since the locations of vehicles are usually different, this has a significant impact on the optimisation result, so the ideal fleet placement must be taken into account.
 - The use of a particular vehicle may be prohibited at a particular pick-up/drop-off point. These exclusion rules may vary depending on the calendar and shift patterns.
 - Vehicles on the road should be blocked from the next optimisation task.
 - GPS tracking data of vehicles should be used for the optimisation.
- Route network management
 - The route network management should be integrated with an online map management system to build the initial route network and automatically track any changes.

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- The practical usability of the road sections may differ from those used in the online map database, so manual correction of the route network and limitations must be taken into account.
- The maximum speed of the road sections is variable and must be taken into account in the optimisation.
- Road sections may have limited accessibility depending on the direction of vehicle passage. These exclusion rules may vary depending on the time of day and shift patterns.
- The time spent on road sections is limited from above for passenger comfort reasons.

3.5. Functional requirements

Identity	Description
REQ-001	Extend the service to any number of industrial parks.
REQ-002	Any number of passenger transport companies can be parameterised in the application
REQ-003	An arbitrary number of commuters from different stops to and from work should be possible on a daily basis, taking into account the changing parameters
REQ-004	Have the application perform an optimised calculation
REQ-005	Ad hoc delivery can be parameterised in the application
REQ-006	Be able to create a periodic (e.g. permanent weekly) timetable in the application
REQ-007	On-demand information should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-008	Working time schedules should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-009	Have the possibility to import demand information in the application
REQ-010	Vehicles should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-011	Central fleet and distributed fleet management should be available in the application
REQ-012	Capacity information should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-013	Route network information should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-014	Weather information should be parameterizable in the application
REQ-015	Realisation characteristics should be measured in the application (e.g. GPS log)
REQ-016	Be able to learn from measuring the realisation characteristics of the application
REQ-017	Send a notification if the application is delayed
REQ-018	Schedule information should also be available on mobile
REQ-019	Make it possible to track vehicles
REQ-020	Provide drivers with a map (current situation) and timetable (stops, scheduled times, number of passengers)

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Identity	Description
REQ-021	Reportage should be possible in the app
REQ-022	The application should be cloud-enabled

3-1. table: Functional requirements

3.6. Non-functional requirements

Identity	Description
REQ-N001	Authentication requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User identification should be done by username/password pair, with the exception of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GPS device where device identification should take place ○ Mobile application where there is no identification
REQ-N002	Authorisation: access to certain functions of the application should be controlled by authorisation
REQ-N003	Maximum simultaneous system users < 20 persons per park Maximum simultaneous mobile users < 500 persons per park
REQ-N004	Maximum annual storage expansion: <100 GB
REQ-N005	Guaranteed application availability: the application must be available between 07:00 and 18:00 on working days
REQ-N006	Maximum downtime: maximum system downtime: 1 working day
REQ-N007	Average number of simultaneous users: < 5 persons per park Average simultaneous mobile users < 50 persons per park
REQ-N008	Maximum response time: < 5 seconds for standard surfaces, < 60 seconds for special surfaces
REQ-N009	Interface design requirements: make the application easy to use
REQ-N010	Archiving requirement: no archiving requirement
REQ-N011	Computational complexity: up to 500 bus stops and 50 vehicles per industrial park
REQ-N012	Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap < 1%
REQ-N013	High performance calculation, i.e. short calculation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
REQ-N014	Expected cost reduction of 20% through optimisation

3-2. table: Non-functional requirements

4. Business processes

4.1. The whole process of the AI-based framework

4-1. figure: Process model: the entire process of an AI-based framework

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4.2. Startup system configuration and setup process

4-2. figure: Startup system configuration and setup process

Main steps:

- Configure partner trunks: where you can add and parameterise factories and transport companies.
- Configure HR trunks: where you can set up shift types, shift groups and work schedules per factory.
- Route network configuration: an automated process whereby the shortest station distances are automatically retrieved from the stations (name, GPS) using a map API, and a route network is constructed to access the stations.

4-3. figure: Generating a route network from stations

- Vehicle placement learning process: the aim is to automatically determine (see Vehicle placement teaching process chapter) which is the most economical fleet configuration based on the route network built and the transport plan. This is essential for the procurement and distribution of vehicles.
- Vehicle fleet configuration: where the vehicles purchased are recorded.

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- Automatic vehicle prioritisation: the purpose is to automatically determine the vehicle priority for the use of vehicles based on the year of the year, climate, environmental rating, capacity and tariff (see Vehicle prioritisation process chapter).
- Install GPS devices: define the GPS device installed on the vehicle, connect it to the vehicle.
- Engine configuration: which includes the configuration of the calculation methods (algorithm selection, solver selection) and the inclusion of the iterators.
- Setting logistic parameters.
- Setting up scheduling parameters.
- Setting GPS device parameters.
- Setting calculation tuning parameters.

4.3. Vehicle placement learning process

4-4. figure: Vehicle placement learning process

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Járműelhelyezés tanítása

Terv: 2018-11-07 - 12:00 - Munkába utazás

Járművek száma: 2

Jármű típusok:

- 14 fős
- 15 fős
- 16Fős**
- 17Fős
- 18 fős
- 19 fős**
- 20Fős
- 21 fős
- 22 fős
- 23Fős
- 24 fős
- 25 fős
- 26 fős
- 27 fős
- 28 fős
- 29 fős
- 30 fős
- 31 fős
- 32 fős
- 33 fős
- 34 fős
- 35 fős**
- 36 fős

Megállók:

- Abony - Abony Bodócs köz
- Abony - Abony Kossuth tér
- Abony - Abony Temeto**
- Abony - Abony, Abonyi Lajos utca
- Abony - Abony, élelmiszerbolt
- Adony - Adony Bajcsy Zsilinszky
- Adony - Adony Dózsa Gy. u.
- Adony - Adony Temeto
- Adony - Adony Templom
- Adony - Adony, Kinizsi u
- Adony - Adony, községháza
- Albertirsa - Albertirsa ABC áruház**
- Albertirsa - Albertirsa autómosó
- Alsónémedi - 5-ös út Alsónémedi Haras:
- Alsónémedi - Alsónémedi 5-ös út Árpád
- Alsónémedi - Alsónémedi Haraszti út 81
- Alsónémedi - Alsónémedi, Szabadság té
- Apaj - Apaj kunszentmiklósi útelágazás
- Áporka - Áporka Áporkai elágazás
- Áporka - Áporka autóbusz-forduló
- Áporka - Áporka Községháza**
- Áporka - Áporka Petöfi Sándor utca
- Apostag - Apostag autóbusz-váróterem

Számítás indítása

4-5. figure: Vehicle placement learning settings

In the vehicle placement learning process, a full evaluation and mathematical optimization is performed as in other cases, with the following differences:

- In this case, the selected plan will include a representative allocation of demands specific to the industrial estate.
- The type and number of vehicles to be learned will be installed at each potential terminal.

As a result, the calculation results obtained will "paint" (identify) the vehicles that are truly the most economical in delivering representative demand.

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4.4. Vehicle prioritisation process

4-6. figure: Vehicle prioritisation process

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Jármű

Fej adatok

Partner: Atlasz busz Kft

Jármű típus: 24 fős

Rendszám: Fizikai 2

Gyártási év: 0

Klimatizált:

Járatszám: 17

Euro környezetvédelmi besorolás: 10

Mentés

Járat logisztikai paraméterek

Járat menetrend paraméterek

Járat GPS paraméterek

Járat prioritás paraméterek

Automatikus jármű prioritálás:

Gyártási év súlya: 25

Klimatizálás súlya: 15

Befogadó méret súlya: 30

Euro környezetvédelmi besorolás súlya: 10

Ár súlya: 20

4-7. figure: Vehicle prioritisation settings

The purpose of vehicle prioritisation is to automatically determine the priority of vehicles to be used, based on their vintage, air conditioning, Euro environmental classification, capacity and tariff, when vehicles are added. In this process, the individual criteria are read and then normalised, i.e. represented as a real number with values between 0 ... 1. In the case where a given encoded criterion would have an opposite effect in the objective function, it undergoes complementary training ($x=1-X$). The coded criteria thus generated are weighted and summed by the weight vector in the system parameters. Since the output value of the process must be between 1...10, the resulting weighted value between 0...1 is multiplied and rounded.

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4.5. The planning process

4-8. figure: Planning process

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When planning the demand, we can talk about individual or - outside the plan - delivery demand and planning-based delivery demand. Planning-based delivery can be of two types:

- Transport demand configured in the HR module: in this case, for the types of shifts, shift groups and work schedules previously set up per factory, the rotation of each shift group is configured, i.e. the days on which they work according to which work schedule. From this configuration and the shift group assignment of the workers, as well as their absence data, the exact transport needs can be generated.

4-9. figure: Generating delivery requests from the HR module

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- Delivery requests configured outside the HR module: in this case, delivery requests can be created either by importing the plan lists or by manually entering them (recording, modifying, deleting).

The screenshot displays the 'Tervezés' (Scheduling) interface. At the top, there are filter options for 'Szűrés' (Filter) including 'Projektok megjelenítése' and 'Lezártak megjelenítése', and a 'Sorok száma' (Number of rows) set to 1000. Below this is a table of transport requests with columns for ID, Tervezett nap (Planned date), Műszak (Shift), Irány (Direction), Státusz (Status), Létrehozva (Created on), Létrehozó (Created by), Módosítva (Modified on), Módosító (Modified by), and Típus (Type). The table contains several rows of data, including entries for 'Haza utazás' (Home trip) and 'Munkába utazás' (Work trip).

Two blue arrows point from the table to other parts of the interface. One arrow points from the 'Munkába utazás' row (ID 13321) to the 'Új terv' (New plan) form. The other arrow points from the 'Munkába utazás' row (ID 13321) to the 'Terv igényei' (Plan requirements) summary.

The 'Új terv' form includes fields for 'Tervezett nap' (Planned date), 'Műszak időpontja' (Shift start time), 'Tartalék idő' (Buffer time), 'Jelenlegi státusz' (Current status), and 'Irány' (Direction). It also has 'Létrehoz' (Create) and 'Számít' (Calculate) buttons.

The 'Terv igényei' summary shows details for a specific plan: 'Tervezett nap' (2018.11.07), 'Műszak időpontja' (06:00:00), 'Irány' (Haza utazás), 'Tartalék idő' (00:20:00), 'Létrehozás ideje' (2018. 11. 02. 10:40:34), 'Létrehozó neve' (AppAdmin), 'Utolsó módosítás ideje' (2018. 11. 02. 10:40:34), and 'Módosító neve' (AppAdmin). Below this is a table of 'Demandid' (Demand ID), 'Állomás' (Station), 'Dolgozók száma' (Number of workers), and 'Gyár' (Factory).

Demandid	Állomás	Dolgozók száma	Gyár
179567	Abony Kossuth tér	1	
179566	Abony, Abonyi Lajos utca	1	
179569	Adony Bajcsy Zsilinszky	1	
179568	Adony Dúzsza Gy. u.	1	
179571	Adony Templom	2	

4-10. figure: Manual recording of transport needs

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4.6. Configuration update process

4-11. figure: Configuration update process

4-12. figure: Fixing exclusions during configuration

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In all cases, the calculation is preceded by a configuration update, which includes the following steps:

- Adding new route network station: i.e. adding new stations according to the needs of factories.
- Add new time constraints: for new stations.
- Add new route network edges: connecting the new stations.
- Update exclusions:
 - The new route network station will define which vehicles are blocked and at what kind of level.
 - The new route network edge will define which vehicles are blocked, in which direction and at what kind of level.
- Addition of new factory distances: in case the factory distance is not calculated from the shortest route on the route network, but from the contractual distance.
- Updating the calendar data: i.e. to include public holidays and public working days other than the weekly working schedule.
- Reimporting employee data: in the case of HR module-based planning, this provides information on the transport needs per station.

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4.7. Calculation process

The initial steps of the calculation are:

- Algorithm type selection: based on the configurations, the algorithm types implemented during the R&D are:
 - Flower petal: an algorithm that breaks down the route network computation into parts, similar to plucking flower petals.
 - Waterflow: an algorithm that performs the route network calculations in a similar way to a flowing water into a valley.
 - Combinatorial: an algorithm based on the prior generation of feasible combinations that satisfy constraints.
 - Fixed schedule: an algorithm based on the scheduling of predefined getting on and getting off times.
 - Implied probability: complete solution to calculate the structure-based route network. Requires much more computation than previous algorithms.
 - Recursive implication: complete solution to compute the loop-based route network. Requires much more computation than previous algorithms.
- Solver type selection: based on configurations, the types of evaluators built in during R&D are:
 - Gurobi: a product of Gurobi Optimization, LLC.
 - CBC: product of COIN-OR Foundation Inc. with Google API.
 - LP: an evaluator from <http://Ipsolve.sourceforge.net/5.5/>.
 - MS: a product of Gurobi Optimization LLC. with limited functionality and Microsoft API.
- System parameter reading.
- Plan aggregation: the purpose of which is to aggregate the demands of the recurring schedules expected according to the recurring workdays into so-called weekly plan demands, in order to make the calculations sufficient to be performed only once per shift.

4-13. figure: Calculation process

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The calculation steps in the evaluation process are iterative and multi-stage, with each iteration level as follows:

- Shift schedule-based parallelisation: which, depending on the configuration, can be e.g.:
 - In case of three shifts, 6:00, 14:00, 22:00 hours schedule,
 - In case of two shifts, 6:00, 18:00 hours schedule.
- Repetition of implementation per spoke: the route network covering the catchment area of industrial parks can be very complex. The combinatorial space required to calculate the optimal result can be as high as 10^{500} combinatorial possibilities in the case of a loop-based model. In order to reduce the number of combinations, the route network can be radially subdivided along natural features (rivers without bridges or mountain ranges impassable for buses or less important transfer points). This type of subdivision is called spoke splitting or spoke heuristics. Accordingly, there is a so-called "spoke" implementation of the above algorithms, which performs the computation in parts, and a so-called "disk" implementation, which performs the computation in one step, which can be set in the computation methods configuration. When the disk type algorithm is selected, the execution in a spoke is naturally interpreted as an execution in a single step.
- Iteration on the iterator configuration: when performing calculations, it may happen that the total bus capacity demand - configured with exclusions - or the time limit set for running buses is not sufficient to serve the planned demands, so the result of a calculation may either succeed or fail. However, the rigid output of the calculation can be made flexible by introducing the so-called iterator configuration. Using the iterator configuration, the number of calculation levels can be specified and the percentage increase of each level compared to the default settings can be configured:
 - The spare capacity of the buses,
 - The bus journey time limit,
 - The levels of exclusions.
- Calculating both directions on a single spoke: the significant computational capacity requirement can be further reduced by splitting the calculation into directions, i.e. calculating the directions to work and home on separate threads. In this case, of course, it will be necessary to merge the results obtained in this way according to the "Direction decomposition" heuristic. Whether the calculations are run with or without directional splitting can be configured in the system parameters.

The next phase is the generation of descriptive systems of equations for the algorithm implementation as follows:

- Generate station descriptor equations to ensure that all passengers waiting at a given station are transported.
- Generate vehicle descriptor equations that do not allow more passengers to board a bus than the allowed capacity.
- Generate probability descriptor equations to determine the probability of departure of a bus.

The next phase is the generation of descriptive equation systems for the route network implementation:

- Generate equations describing the route network, which aims to define the route network traversal according to graph-theoretic rules.
- Generation of graph-theoretic heuristic equations to improve the performance of the evaluation engine. Their use can significantly reduce the number of access combinations and running time.
- Generation of exclusion equations to restrict certain vehicle route-station or vehicle route-edge combinations based on exclusion definitions.

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- Generation of a cost description equation to aggregate the cost factors of the transport per bus and to produce the cost function to be optimised.
- Generation of time limit equations, where the available running time is limited for each bus.

The next step is the multithreaded evaluation of the generated equation systems. This requires, however, that the previously generated route network patterns described above are read and used in the evaluation.

After the equations have been evaluated, the next step is to draw up the bus schedule, which consists of the following steps:

- Route planning: the aim is to arrange the set of stations to be visited in an optimal order for each vehicle, based on the calculations. Route planning is only necessary at stations where the onward journey can be made in several directions.
- Use of GPS-based learning speeds and arrival times: the aim is to generate predicted data from GPS data (vehicle identification, route network edge identification, weather plan data (snow, rain, fog, wind, ice), traffic intensity, direction of travel, day of work, periodic dates (day of the week, day of the month, month of the year), speeds measured from GPS data) and use them to build a bus schedule that approximates reality as closely as possible. The forecast data are as follows:
 - Predicted average speeds per route network edge per vehicle,
 - Predicted arrival times per route network station per vehicle.
- Accounting of calculation results: the aim is to save the resulting schedules, carrier and factory financial data.

After the evaluation of the parallel calculations on the way to work and on the way home, the results are combined according to the "Direction decomposition" heuristic, which we have already described above.

The final step of the evaluation is to replicate the calculation results of the aggregated demands into weekly plans to the initial demands.

4.8. Calculation check

4-14. figure: Calculation check

Checking the calculation includes checking the bus schedules, checking the number of buses booked (direction, occupancy, cost) and checking the profit totals. If all the outputs are correct, the process ends with the acceptance of the calculation. If the outputs received are not correct, the calculation can be cancelled, the configuration can then be modified and the calculation can be re-run.

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4-15. figure: Calculation check interfaces

4.9. Evaluation management process

4-16. figure: Evaluation management process

When the calculation is accepted, the system outputs are automatically displayed, which are:

- E-mail notification based results,
- Mobile bus schedule results,
- TV display results,
- Software user interface results.

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4.10. GPS-based learning process

4-17. figure: GPS-based learning process

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The aim of the process is to produce predicted data from measured empirical data, and then use it to build a schedule that approximates reality as closely as possible. The steps in the process are:

- A triggering event:
 - Scheduled event, which is a pre-configurable time in the system.
 - Manual start event, which can be called from the Settings/GPS-based learning start menu.
- Implement the following steps for each upcoming demand plan,
- Perform the following steps for each vehicle-route network edge combination,
- Parallel reading of inputs, covering:
 - Vehicle identification,
 - Identifying route network edges,
 - Weather fact data: snow, rain, fog, wind, icing,
 - Weather plan data: snow, rain, fog, wind, icing,
 - Traffic intensity,
 - Direction: to work or to home,
 - Working day,
 - Periodic dates: day of the week, day of the month, month of the year,
 - Speeds measured from GPS log data.
- Preparation of inputs, which includes for these data:
 - Data backup to a database,
 - Data representation and export to the Tensorflow module.
- The implementation of the Tensorflow module, the steps of which are:
 - Building a neural network model:
 - Read input data file,
 - Rescale data to the interval 0.. 1,
 - Write the data to the log file,
 - Cutting the learning data from the input,
 - Cut the test data from the input,
 - Build the neural network,
 - Definition of weights,
 - Definition of a hypothesis function,
 - Defining the cost/loss function,
 - Define an optimization method,
 - Create a session,
 - Initialisation of variables,
 - Learning phase: learning a neural network while logging the learning steps,
 - Test/prediction phase:
 - Run test data on the learned network,
 - Data conversion of the resulting prediction,
 - Write the resulting prediction to a console,
 - Write the resulting prediction to a file.
- Output saving, which includes prediction:

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- Import data from the Tensorflow module,
- Data backup to a database.
- The results obtained are used in the calculation and scheduling of the forecast data as follows:
 - Predicted average speeds per route network edge per vehicle,
 - Predicted arrival times per route network station per vehicle.

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4.11. Dynamic schedule update and notification process

4-18. figure: Dynamic schedule update and notification process

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Járat menetrend paraméterek

Menetrend visszahatás történjen-e:

Küszöb paraméter (másodperc):

Várható menetrend bekapcsolása - TV kijelző:

Várható menetrend bekapcsolása - Mobilinfó:

Várható menetrend bekapcsolása - PDF menetrend:

Várható menetrend bekapcsolása - Program listák:

4-19. figure: Dynamic schedule update settings

The purpose of the process is to automatically update the schedule outputs displayed by the system if the delay exceeds the allowable threshold. It is also responsible for notifying the carrier and the service provider of the delay. Steps in the process:

- Triggering event: GPS data from buses,
- Analysing the extent of divergence:
 - Measuring and calculating the time difference from GPS data,
 - Read the maximum allowable threshold from the system parameters,
 - If the divergence is less than the threshold, the process stops.
- Automatic recalculation of expected bus schedule data, whereby the expected data is stored alongside the planned timetable data.
- Notification, change management: for each type of schedule output there is a system parameter setting that determines whether the output should display planned or expected data. Accordingly, each output is notified or updated:
 - E-mail notification is sent to the service provider,
 - A notification is sent to the carrier if this has not yet been done for this vehicle,

4-20. figure: Dynamic schedule update in the driver application

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- Mobile bus schedule will be updated if the expected data is relevant,

4-21. figure: Dynamic bus schedule update in the employee mobile app

- TV display schedule will be updated if there the expected data is relevant,

4-22. figure: Dynamic bus schedule update on the factory TV display

- The software user interface will be updated if the expected data there is relevant.

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5. Statistics

The AI base framework was tested over a two-year period, i.e. from 01.01.2020 to 31.12.2021, according to the following criteria:

- Computational runtime: we expect the majority of cases to be completed within 90 seconds.
- Computational accuracy: we expect the majority of cases to be above 99% accuracy.
- Optimisation impact: measured in terms of distance travelled, fuel and emissions. The pre-optimisation state is the state before the system is implemented, for which we have estimated data. We expect the savings from optimisation to be around 20%.

These statistics have been tested for 5 live sites (industrial parks), the exact names of the sites cannot be disclosed due to lack of consent from the relevant factories or industrial parks.

5.1. Statistics of industrial park “A”

5-1. figure: Industrial park “A” – accuracy of calculation

5-2. figure: Industrial park “A” – runtime of calculation

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
		Date: 2021.12.23.
		Rating: public

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	511	1 409 632	677 007	227 089	107 647	601 786	285 264	52,60%
14:00	465	835 422	673 627	134 073	107 425	355 294	284 676	19,88%
22:00	455	1 148 486	606 555	189 940	98 456	503 342	260 908	48,16%

5-1. table: Industrial park "A" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-3. figure: Industrial park "A" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.2. Statistics of industrial park "B"

5-4. figure: Industrial park "B" – accuracy of calculation

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
		Date: 2021.12.23.
		Rating: public

5-5. figure: Industrial park "B" – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	713	2 817 837	2 334 061	440 272	375 346	1 166 720	994 667	14,75%
8:00	498	560 796	383 317	75 495	57 085	200 061	151 275	24,39%
16:00	497	530 216	372 705	71 650	55 810	189 874	147 897	22,11%
18:00	713	2 727 289	2 287 602	426 948	370 496	1 131 411	981 813	13,22%

5-2. table: Industrial park "B" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-6. figure: Industrial park "B" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.3. Statistics of industrial park “C”

5-7. figure: Industrial park “C” – accuracy of calculation

5-8. figure: Industrial park “C” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		Savings (%)
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	
6:00	705	2 202 860	1 176 162	373 153	193 764	988 856	513 474	48,07%
14:00	704	2 158 293	1 095 451	378 376	179 613	1 002 696	475 975	52,53%
18:00	699	1 196 534	556 096	167 792	69 125	444 648	183 182	58,80%
22:00	705	2 132 162	1 022 633	357 200	165 841	946 579	439 477	53,57%

5-3. table: Industrial park “C” – datas of CO₂ emission

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
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		Rating: public

5-9. figure: Industrial park "C" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.4. Statistics of industrial park "D"

5-10. figure: Industrial park "D" – accuracy of calculation

5-11. figure: Industrial park "D" – runtime of calculation

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
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Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		Savings (%)
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	
6:00	78	35 794	17 993	3 982	2 010	10 551	5 326	49,52%
14:00	76	40 011	20 286	4 452	2 251	11 797	5 965	49,43%
22:00	69	26 503	16 010	3 034	1 792	8 040	4 749	40,93%

5-4. table: Industrial park "D" – datas of CO₂ emission

5-12. figure: Industrial park "D" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

5.5. Statistics of industrial park "E"

5-13. figure: Industrial park "E" – accuracy of calculation

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
		Date: 2021.12.23.
		Rating: public

5-14. figure: Industrial park “E” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO ₂ emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	675	2 393 785	1 199 989	392 633	193 414	1 040 477	512 547	50,74%
14:00	641	1 519 870	1 147 297	224 305	183 176	594 408	485 415	18,34%
18:00	393	1 094 357	180 031	174 449	18 409	462 291	48 785	89,45%
22:00	643	1 440 665	1 127 450	237 027	179 646	628 122	476 062	24,21%

5-5. table: Industrial park “E” – datas of CO₂ emission

5-15. figure: Industrial park “E” – characteristics of CO₂ emission

	Hercules Routes: Presentation of business requirements, business processes and statistics	ID: HR-BR+BP+S
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		Rating: public

6. Conclusions

In this document, we have reviewed the business requirements identified during the development of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Flights", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364, and the business processes and statistics of the resulting system.

In developing this framework, the objective was to implement a service package that would optimise long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. By choosing the right vehicles and routes, we hoped to achieve significant cost savings and reduce emissions and noise pollution. In line with this, our key measurable expectations for the system were:

- Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
- High performance computation, i.e. short computation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Expected 20% reduction in cost and environmental impact

These measurable results have been analysed on the basis of statistics from 5 live sites (industrial parks) for the last two years, i.e. from 01/01/2020 to 31/12/2021:

- Based on the measured results, we can state that both the accuracy of the calculation results and the calculation time have been met in all cases, and in the case of smaller industrial parks, shorter calculation times and often only 100% quality results were obtained.
- Our expectations for cost reductions were significantly influenced by the transport needs of the factories and the route network in the vicinity of the park. In terms of cost savings per industrial park, we achieved the expected average savings of 20% in all cases, but for some parks we exceeded this level by far and achieved average savings of over 40%.

Overall, our work has been successful and we are confident that the framework will be rolled out to other industrial parks in the hope of a more economical, greener, flexible package of route planning and passenger transport services.

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